

Poolbeg combined cycle gas turbine project

Cooling water pumphouse

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SYNOPSIS

This paper describes the design and construction of a Cooling Water Pumphouse servicing the Poolbeg 470 MW Combined Cycle Development. It outlines in detail the construction and sinking of a concrete caisson and covers the Temporary Works associated with the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Project

The Electricity Supply Board is currently completing a project to extend Poolbeg Generating Station by the addition of 470MW of generating plant.

The new plant will comprise 2 No.155MW (nominal rating) combustion turbines and 1No.160MW steam turbine. The plant is capable of operating in two modes, simple cycle and combined cycle. In simple cycle mode, the exhaust gases of the combustion turbines are discharged to atmosphere via a bypass stack at approximately 550°C. In combined cycle these gases are diverted to the unfired Heat Recovery Boilers (HRBs) which generate steam, which in turn drives a steam turbine and generator, thus providing additional power output without requiring additional fuel. Utilising the exhaust gases in this manner enables a simple cycle efficiency of about 34% to be increased to a combined-cycle efficiency of over 50% with considerable environmental benefits. This efficiency represents one of the most economical uses of primary fuel available. The primary fuel used here to fire the combustion turbines is natural gas. Distillate oil can be used as an alternative.

Phase I of the Project comprising the first 155MW combustion turbine has been in operation since 1994. Phase II, the second 155MW combustion turbine is at present being commissioned. With the completion of Phase III in late 1999, the combined-cycle plant, will be capable of delivering approximately 470MW of power to the National Grid and Poolbeg, with a total

generating capacity of 990MW will then be the largest generating station in the country. An independent Cooling Water Pumphouse (the subject of this paper) was constructed to provide cooling water for the new unit. The civil works contract was awarded to Jons Civil Engineering Co. Ltd. (Jons) in September 1997 and construction began on site on November 11th 1997. The critical path date for provision of access to the plant installation contractor by October 1st 1998 was achieved and the contract is due for completion by the end of December 1998.

1.2 Brief History of the Caisson

The focal point in this paper is the concrete caisson used to construct the new Cooling Water Pumphouse. This technique dates back to the ancient civilisations of Egypt, Burma and India who used it to construct bridge foundations. When rivers were low in the dry season, timber, brick and masonry wells were built on the river bed. Material beneath the piers was then excavated by swimmers, by hand, thereby gradually sinking the pier. Crude farm implements were used and depths of up to 6m were achieved, the main limitation being the swimmer's ability to 'hold his breath'.

Hand excavation was later replaced by grabs and sand pumps and in 1915, the piers for the Hardinge Bridge over the lower Ganges were sunk to a depth of 48m below water by this means. Other caisson built bridges include the Oakland Bay-San Francisco Bridge (depth 69m) and the Jumana River Bridge in Bangladesh (depth 105m).

Closer to home, ESB has constructed the

Cooling Water Pumphouses for both Ringsend and the existing Poolbeg power stations using this technique.

2. COOLING WATER SYSTEM

2.1 General Description

In steam turbines, water is used in two separate cycles: purified water in the steam cycle and untreated water in the cooling cycle. Boiler water which is converted to steam has to have a high standard of purity in order to avoid damage by impurities to boiler tubes or turbine blades. After use in the turbine, the spent steam is condensed and conserved for recycling to the boiler. Condensing is brought about by discharging the steam into a steel chamber (the condenser) which is penetrated by rows of metal tubes through which cooling water (which does not have to be of high quality) is flowing. The steam condensate is returned to the boiler for reuse; the cooling water which, in the case of Poolbeg is abstracted from the River Liffey, will have gained the heat lost by the steam during condensation and is then returned to the Liffey for natural cooling.

The cooling water which is required to condense the spent steam is drawn from the Liffey at a rate of 4.7cu.m/sec. by each of 2, single stage, mixed flow, centrifugal pumps operating at a nominal head of 18m, fed to the condenser through the intake culvert and finally routed to the existing channel outfall at Poolbeg through an outlet culvert for discharge back to the Liffey downstream of the Pumphouse. (Ref. Fig. 1).

FIG 1.

2.2 Cooling Water System Design Considerations.

Planning Conditions

The cooling water system design is governed by limitations imposed in the 'Licence to discharge Trade Effluent to Waters', issued as part of the planning conditions by Dublin Corporation. The licence takes account of the cooling water requirements of the existing station together with those of the new unit.

The key considerations governing the C.W. system design are as follows:

- Maximum rate of water intake/discharge for the total Poolbeg station: 26.4 cu.m/sec
- Maximum total volume discharged per day: 2.3×10^6 cu.m
- Temperature in the estuary should not be artificially increased by more than 1.5°C above ambient at depth greater than 1.5m from the surface except in certain stated locations.
- The temperature of the cooling water effluent discharge as measured at the existing bridge over the cooling water outfall channel should not exceed the temperature of the ambient estuarine water by more than 10°C.

- The concentration of total residual chlorine should not exceed 0.1 mg/l.

Under normal operating conditions for the new plant, each of the 2 pumps extracts 4.7cu.m/sec (i.e. 9.4cu.m/sec. in total). The existing station at Poolbeg extracts 15.4cu.m/sec. The overall permitted figure of 26.4 cu.m/sec is therefore not exceeded.

Temperature effects were assessed by extensive thermal plume modelling of the Liffey and Dublin Bay area by ESB International (ESBI) and were found to be within acceptable levels.

Fishery Considerations

The size of the intake openings is governed by the limitation on intake water velocity to allow smolt to escape. An intake flow of 4.7 cu.m/sec through an opening 3.6m high by 4.7m wide gives an approach velocity of less than the recommended 0.3m/sec.

Hydraulic Model

A physical hydraulic model of the Pumphouse at a scale of 1:10, was constructed in order to optimise the hydraulic performance of the structure and minimise the likelihood of turbulent flow, thereby ensuring that the pumps operate at their design capacity. As a result of the model tests, a number of key features were incorporated into the Pumphouse layout. See figures 2 and 4.

- Backwall splitter behind the pumps
- Pier nose shaped similar to a half cylinder
- Splays to the back and side walls of the pump chambers.
- Entry cone just below the bell mouth.
- Intake openings below water level at all stages of the tide
- Curtain wall soffit level - 2.0m.O.D. upstream of the pump which forces the water to enter the bell mouth from below.
- Floor level at -4.8m.O.D.

3. COOLING WATER PUMPHOUSE DESIGN

3.1 Layout (Ref. Fig.2)

Cooling water entering the Pumphouse carries debris in varying quantities and must undergo a multi-stage screening process before entering the culvert. This screening is carried out in two stages: on fixed coarse screens and moving drumscreens. The coarse screens, clear opening width 51mm, prevent large items of debris from entering the Pumphouse. This debris is removed naturally by changing tide levels and currents. The water passing the coarse

FIG 2.

screens is further filtered on the rotating 10m dia. drumscreen which has a nominal mesh size of 5mm x 5mm. Trash arrested on the mesh is carried up by the trash lifting trays and is removed by backwashing into a discharge trough on the roof deck for collection in a debris basket. Drumscreen wash water contains higher levels of chlorine (see below) than permitted for discharge to the Liffey and must therefore discharge back into the Pumphouse. This wash water undergoes a further stage of filtration in a Rotostrainer or 'mini-drumscreen', before discharging back into the Pumphouse just upstream of the drumscreen, the additional filtration being required to prevent a cumulative build up of smaller particle debris on the drumscreen.

In addition to the coarse screens, fine mesh screens are provided to exclude smolt from the Pumphouse during the period mid-March to mid-May.

As well as undergoing a screening process, cooling water must also be chlorinated to prevent the growth of shellfish within the culverts. Water, abstracted from within the Pumphouse by dedicated chlorination water pumps, is routed to the Chlorination Building (located to the rear of the Pumphouse) for dosing before being returned for injection just inside the front wall.

The screened and chlorinated water abstracted by each pump discharges into two rising mains which merge into a single busmain to the rear of the pumphouse. From here the cooling water is routed to the intake culvert via a thrust block. Two auxiliary pumps, which feed auxiliary plant associated with the turbo-generator or the boiler, are located just upstream of the main pumps in separate chambers.

Sealing of the intake opes for pumping dry of the chamber is achieved by the installation of dambeams located in the inner guide which normally houses the coarse screens. A bi-directional gantry crane is sited at the North face of the pumphouse for removal and installation of dambeams, coarse and smolt screens.

3.2 Site Investigations

Geological Setting of the Site

Poolbeg Generating Station is located on the southside of Dublin some 4km from the city centre at the mouth of the Liffey. Many site investigations associated with various phases of the station development have been conducted at Poolbeg over the last 40 years.

The site is located above a buried glacial valley which runs NW to SE across the present course of the river Liffey. The depth to rock reduces sharply across the site, being greatest (i.e. close to the bottom of the valley) within the river at the Bull Wall and reducing as one moves south. The general geological succession at Poolbeg is outlined below.

Site Investigation for the Pumphouse

Because of anticipated difficulties in achieving a seal or cutoff for a sheet pile cofferdam, it was decided to tender the project on the assumption that it would be constructed as an open caisson. Tenderers were however given the option of submitting alternative proposals in addition to the tendered scheme. Site investigation would therefore need to provide sufficient information to permit development of both a caisson and alternative schemes.

The key factors requiring determination in the investigation were seen to be as follows:

- Hardness/Density of strata through which caisson would be sunk for assessment of excavatability
- Magnitude of adhesion likely to be developed between caisson walls and soils
- Strength and compressibility of strata below base of Pumphouse for bearing capacity and settlement determinations
- Permeability of the strata surrounding and below the projected depth of the pumphouse for assessment of the required length of sheetpiles in a

cofferdam alternative construction method.

The site investigations for the Pumphouse were carried out in two phases during the period June 1996 to October 1997.

The initial investigation comprised 6 boreholes : 5 located within the proposed footprint of the pumphouse and 1 outside the envelope in the area to be dredged. The boreholes were advanced by cable percussion techniques from a floating pontoon. Rock was proved by rotary coring in three of these holes and by open hole drilling in one. Sampling was alternated with Standard Penetration tests throughout the cable percussion length. Bulk disturbed samples were retained from granular deposits and undisturbed U100 samples from cohesive deposits (or piston samples in the case of very soft cohesive deposits).

Tests from the following range were carried out on recovered samples:

- moisture content
- liquid and plastic limits
- particle size distribution (fine and coarse)
- Consolidated undrained triaxial
- One dimensional consolidation test
- Split and description of untested U100 samples (to potentially identify thin lenses that might not have been noted during boring)

Following completion of the 1996 investigation, the projected conditions through which the caisson was to be sunk were seen to be as shown in Figure 3. Of particular concern to the project was the presence of a soft silt layer, which was picked up in some of the boreholes, but not in others. The layer was seen to be located between the upper and lower gravels and close to the projected toe level of the caisson, which was originally fixed at -8.5m.O.D.

Stratigraphical Sequence	Typical Level Range (O.D Poolbeg)
MADE GROUND (Comprising hydraulically placed sand)	From +5m to 0m
ALLUVIAL DEPOSITS (Comprising medium dense to dense sands and gravels, occasional silt bands)	From 0m to between -11m and -13m
PORT CLAY (Comprising stiff overconsolidated silty clay, occasional sandy bands)	From between -11m and -13m to between- 17m and -25m)
GLACIAL GRAVELS (Comprising dense gravels)	From between -17m and -25m to between -32m and -35m (occasionally absent)
BEDROCK (Hard grey argillaceous limestone)	From between -17m and -35m

Outside the NW corner of the Pumphouse the existing bed level was 2.5m lower than the remainder of the bed on the Pumphouse footprint. This was as a result of dredging associated with the intake for the existing Poolbeg pumphouse. The borehole in this area (BH6/96) revealed SPT N values as low as 3 at -8m.O.D.

After a review of the investigation results it was decided to revise the design toe level of the caisson to -9.2m.O.D. thereby ensuring it was founded in the gravels.

Supplementary Site Investigation

In October 1997 a supplementary site investigation was carried out with the primary intention of examining material to be dredged from the riverbed to provide a basin for water intake at the front of the Pumphouse. The investigation comprised eight cable percussion boreholes to a maximum depth of 5m (maximum depth to be dredged). Also, an additional borehole (BH20/97) (see fig 3) was sunk at the NW corner of the Pumphouse to verify consistency of the bed strata. The results of this borehole enabled closer definition of the geometry of the soft silt layer, which was assigned an undrained strength of 18kN/m2 in temporary works stability calculations. The implications of this layer are considered further later in this paper.

Prediction of Caisson

Sinking Characteristics

It was apparent from the fieldwork of the site investigation that sinking of the caisson would be primarily through granular deposits. An assessment of the interface friction that would need to be overcome in the sinking process was made by modelling the caisson walls as driven piles in terms of the lateral pressure that would be imposed by the surrounding ground. The interface friction to be overcome would then be the product of the lateral earth pressure and tangent of the angle of internal friction of the

soil. The angle of internal friction was correlated from SPT N values. The in-situ lateral earth pressure coefficient K_0 can be equated to $(1 - \sin\phi)$. The sinking of the caisson imparts an increase in lateral earth pressure. This increase in lateral earth pressure was calculated in the same manner as for a driven pile. In this way the interface friction was estimated at intermediate stages of sinking and compared to the weight of the caisson.

Using this method of calculation it was predicted that the weight of the caisson (approximately 4,000 tonne at full height) would be sufficient to progress the sinking by intercellular excavation alone to a level of approximately -4m.O.D. Beyond this, it was predicted that supplementary methods would be required. A review of published literature suggested that a wide range of interface friction values (ranging from 10kN/m2 to 100kN/m2 depending on soil type) had been back-analysed from caisson experience around the world. It was clear that contingency measures would need to be in position to cater for the event of caisson 'hang-up'.

Bearing Capacity and Settlement

Bearing capacity and settlement are governed by net bearing pressure. Because of the cellular nature of the caisson the net bearing pressure at the level of the toe of the caisson (after excavation of soil from within the cells and pouring the concrete floor of the Pumphouse) is only approximately 25kN/m2 if considered as a uniformly distributed load. In reality, the distribution of load to the caisson footprint is not uniform and the strata below experience an increase in stress which is limited by the interface friction between the soil and the caisson walls.

The caisson design envisaged bearing on medium dense gravels. The boreholes indicated that at a toe level of -9.2m.O.D this should be achieved. It was however

recognised that the soft silt layer was not far above this level. Consolidation settlement in this soft layer was checked for the event that sections of the caisson toe were to bear on it under a pressure of 25kN/m2. Due to the low net pressure, settlement under this scenario would be less than 15mm, which was considered acceptable.

Bearing failure was assessed in terms of local bearing failure under the toe of the caisson (global bearing failure being considered unrealistic due to the depth of the caisson). A factor of safety in excess of 2.5 was confirmed for local bearing failure.

3.3 Structural Design (Ref. fig.4)

Formation Level

The level of the floor slab in the pumphouse is governed by a number of factors: drowned depth required for pump operations, ambient tidal conditions, head losses through the screens and head losses at the pump intake. The floor level taking these parameters into account varies from -4.6 m.O.D at intake to -4.8 m.O.D in the pump chamber. As noted above, the structure is founded in the gravel layer at -9.2 m.O.D and the area to the underside of the floor slab (the 'plug') is built up in mass concrete. The existing bed level in the area varied from +2.5 m.O.D at the Bull Wall to -2.5 m.O.D at the NW face of the pumphouse.

Construction Options

A number of possible construction options were considered:

- Caisson construction on a sand island in the river
- Construction in the dry in a sheet piled cofferdam.
- Floated in caissons (The Ringsend pumphouse was constructed by this method)

FIG 3

FIG 4.

It was decided to tender the Pumphouse as option (a) above, i.e. as a caisson constructed on a sand island in the Liffey; the sand island being protected by rock armoured embankments and geotextiles. Tenderers were given the option of submitting, in addition to the tendered schemes, their own preferred construction methodology. This would allow tenderers to bring the benefits of their own individual experience and expertise to the project.

As expected, the alternatives proposed were for options (b) and (c) above. These options were analysed in detail to determine the most cost-effective solution while taking account of the associated risks.

Floated-in caisson

The use of floated-in caissons would necessitate the preparation of the riverbed at -9.2 m.O.D or over 14m below and adjacent to the Bull Wall, a structure of considerable heritage value. This would necessitate major sheet piling works to protect the Bull Wall during construction. Further, a casting yard for the caissons with easy access to the river was not immediately available.

The Ringsend pumphouse lent itself to this method as it was built in a location remote from restrictions imposed by proximity of sensitive structures. The situation here is however very different. A floated-in caisson system was therefore not considered further.

Sheet piled cofferdam

Construction in the dry within a sheet piled cofferdam offered many attractions:

- single stage construction.
- no under water concreting.
- casting of intake openings and building in of screen and dambeam guides as the structure was built.
- less problems in sealing the structure.

The main concern with this method was the ability to effectively seal the cofferdam. While the site investigations did not indicate the presence of sand lenses in the Port Clay, it is well documented elsewhere that they do exist. In spite of the many attractions offered, the potential for a 'blow' in the cofferdam could not be completely excluded. A setback such as this was likely to take a considerable length of time to remedy. Unlike many other projects where the overall project programme contained some float for contingencies, the Poolbeg pumphouse had to meet the overall project key target dates. Consequential losses in generating revenue meant that delay was not an option.

After much deliberation, this method of construction was ruled out.

In-situ caisson

The remaining option was to construct the pumphouse as a caisson on a 'sand island' in the River Liffey and to lower it to its final level by grab excavation through the hollow caisson structure. This method was used for the existing pumphouse, 50 m upstream and had the lowest associated risk.

The construction method adopted differed from the tendered scheme only by the inclusion of a sheet piled wall to contain the sand island and to reduce the likelihood of fines washout interfering with the existing pumphouse operations.

In September 1997, Jons Civil Engineering Co. Ltd. (Jons) was appointed as Contractor for the Works.

Caisson Design

The caisson is effectively a hollow concrete cellular box, 27.9m long, 13m wide and 14.2m high (Ref. fig. 5). The roof structure, when in place, adds a further 1.5m giving an

overall Pumphouse height of 15.7m from toe level at -9.2m.O.D to deck level at +6.5 m.O.D. Finished floor level varies from -4.6 m.O.D at intake to - 4.8 m.O.D at the pump chamber. When the caisson reaches the final formation level, a mass concrete 'plug' 2.6m thick is poured below water to seal the structure. The plug wedges between the tapered cutting shoes and cannot lift. When the plug concrete has gained sufficient strength, the caisson is pumped out, the internal temporary cross walls removed and the floor slab is poured followed by the internal walls and slabs.

Below floor level at -4.6m.O.D the cross walls comprise stiff reinforced concrete beams rigidly connected to the perimeter and central spine wall to form the stiff hollow box structure. These cross beams ultimately become an integral part of the floor slab. The internal cross walls above floor level comprise temporary precast concrete beams 900mm x 900mm which brace the external walls and provide ballast for the sinking operation. These are removed before the permanent internal walls and floors are constructed.

The caisson incorporates a number of features to assist the sinking process. The four perimeter walls taper off at toe level to form the main cutting shoes (Ref. Fig. 6). The central spine wall and cross walls also taper off into cutting shoes but 700mm higher than the perimeter walls. The perimeter walls therefore perform the main cutting operation while the internal walls act as a control on the sinking process to prevent too rapid a drop rate. These also divide the caisson into separate cells for systematic controlled excavation and sinking. Rolled steel channels are fitted to the cutting shoes as a protection measure.

FIG 5.

Cutting shoe detail

FIG 6.

The Pumphouse structural design considered the separate situations where:

- The caisson is in the 'Temporary' condition subject to its self-weight, sinking induced stresses and also backfill and external hydrostatic pressures when pumped dry.
- The Pumphouse has been fully constructed and is subject to external wave, hydrostatic and backfill conditions and also installed plant loads.

The fundamental criterion in the design was that the caisson, when pumped dry and with the plug in place, the temporary walls removed and before construction of the permanent walls and slabs, should have a factor of safety of 1.1 against flotation. In addition, a number of other possible structural situations required investigation. It was considered possible that as the caisson sank it could get 'hung-up' on boulders or hard spots requiring the walls to act as beams. Two possible support conditions for the main NS walls/beams were therefore considered:

- The caisson is 'hung-up' on boulders at the N & S extremities.
- The caisson is 'hung-up' on boulders at one end and a point 2/3 of its length from that end thereby forming a 9m approx. cantilever.

Member sizes based on flotation criteria

were however found to be more than adequate to meet any additional beam action requirements.

The structure was designed to BS 8007. Concrete was Grade C40 except in the plug where C50 was used for early strength gain. Minimum cover to reinforcement was 65mm. High yield steel was used in all cases and generally minimum reinforcement only was required.

4.0 CW PUMPHOUSE CONSTRUCTION

4.1 Site Location and Construction Constraints

The site is located in close proximity to the existing cooling water pumphouse and to the overhead fuel supply pipe bridge which services the present Poolbeg Power Station (Ref. Fig. 1). It was a specific condition of the Contract that the construction methods employed had to ensure that no interference could occur with the operations of the existing station. The Pumphouse is also located adjacent to the Dublin Corporation brick lined sewer and the Dublin Port Bull Wall both of which are structures of considerable heritage value. In addition, there was the added challenge of working within a confined site area.

In order to pre-empt problems, the Contractor prepared detailed method statements and safety plans for review by ESBI before commencement of construction. Good relationships between

FIG 7.

Jons as Contractor, ESBI and Dublin Port ensured that the works progressed with minimum disruption.

4.2 Temporary Works Design

The temporary works involved the construction of a sheet pile cofferdam enclosing an area 40.2m long by 32.4m wide in the Liffey just off the Bull Wall which would retain sand fill placed within its envelope at a level of +2.5m.O.D (Ref. Fig.7). The sand surface would then provide a casting platform for the caisson, protected from damaging wave and tidal actions. The existing bed level varied from +2.5m.O.D at the Bull Wall to +0m.O.D. at the NE corner of the cofferdam and -2.5m.O.D. at the NW corner, this lower level being due to dredging of the bed for the existing C.W. Pumphouse. The design of the cofferdam was based on a planned casting and sinking sequence as follows:

- Infill the cofferdam to +2.5m.O.D
- Cast caisson to a height of 8.6m
- Sink caisson 6.5m to -4.0m.O.D.
- Construct caisson to its full 14.5m height (i.e. 8.0m above sand island level)

- Sink caisson 5.2m to -9.2m.O.D.

Variation in bed level around the perimeter resulted in the required assessment of 2 separate design situations for the sheet pile cofferdam:

- where the bed level is +0m.O.D. or higher (here a sheet pile wall was used)
- where bed level is below +0m.O.D (in the vicinity of the NW corner where a lowest level of 2.5m.O.D was recorded and where a bulkhead comprising an outer line of sheet piles tied to an inner line was used).

Cantilever Sheet Pile Design

Where the bed level was +0m.O.D or above, a cantilever sheet pile section was adopted. The sheet piles had to be designed to cater for a wide range of load scenarios/combinations that could arise during the course of construction:

- A tide level range of 5m
- The lateral load transferred by surcharge weight of the caisson as construction progressed

- The lateral surcharge load of construction traffic which was taken as 10kN/m²

The critical failure modes were seen to be as follows:

- Instability of the cofferdam due to excessive active earth pressures
- Deep rotational slip failure below the level of the sheet pile

The bearing pressure exerted by the caisson (immediately below the cutting edge) at the projected critical stages of construction were:

Caisson Height 'm'	Bearing Pressure kN/m ²
2.6	65
8.6	210

The sheet piling was assessed in accordance with BS 8002. Stability was checked using the lumped F.O.S. method (CIRIA 104) and a further check to Eurocode 7 was carried out.

The analysis indicated that the piles should penetrate to -6.5 m.O.D (They were subsequently driven to - 8.0 m.O.D as an added precautionary measure). A section modulus of 1007cm³/m of wall was required. The piles used, based on driveability considerations have a section modulus of 2500 cm³/m of wall.

Bulkhead Design

Where the bed level dropped below +0m.O.D at the NW corner of the cofferdam, a cantilever sheet pile cofferdam was shown to be inadequate. Here, a bulkhead comprising an outer line of sheet piles driven to -8m.O.D tied to an inner line driven to -6m.O.D was adopted.

The Bulkhead in the NW corner was analysed for the following critical failure modes:

- Overall stability against shear failure with the caisson constructed to a height of 8.6m with toe at +0.5m.O.D.
- Overturning of the bulkhead due to lateral pressures of fill, water, caisson and construction traffic.
- Failure of the outer sheet pile around the upper tie road.

4.3 Temporary Works Construction

Work on the construction of the cofferdam started on November 12th 1997. The first task was the removal of rock armour which had been placed along the Bull Wall during construction of the existing C.W. Pumphouse. Following this, within the cofferdam area, soft riverbed material was removed down to +0m.O.D in order to provide an island formation consistent in both texture and level.

The sheet pile cofferdam comprised Larssen 606 piles throughout which extended 4.0m above the +2.5m.O.D. surface level to provide protection from wave action. The sheet piling was constructed in two halves dictated by the reach capabilities of the IHI CCH 500 Crane: the southern half from the Bull Wall; the northern half from a temporary platform which extended a distance of 35m into the river. The platform comprised crane mats on double 610x305 steel beams supported on 36m long steel piles. The bridge was braced back to the wall of the cofferdam with 12m long struts. The piles were driven using a BHP 1.5t Hydraulic Hammer to depths ranging from -6.0m.O.D to -8.0m.O.D depending on the level and stratification of the riverbed along the island perimeter. Sheet piles along the Bull Wall were driven to -11m.O.D. An internal L shaped bulkhead was constructed in the NW corner to strengthen the cofferdam where the bed level dropped to -2.5m.O.D. In addition, rubble backfill was placed outside the NW corner of the cofferdam to -1.0 m.O.D to provide the required level of stability. On completion of piling, the platform structure was removed and the cofferdam then filled with sand stockpiled from adjacent site excavations. The continuous hydraulic motion of the tide assisted in consolidating the sand which was subsequently compacted to the specified density with vibrating rollers. A channel was formed along the inside perimeter of the cofferdam to collect water entering through the pile clutches. Sand and coal dust was applied to the outside face of the sheet piles which greatly assisted in reducing the inflow. Sumps were formed in the NW and SW corners of the cofferdam which allowed the island water level to be controlled using a maximum of three six inch submersible pumps at high tide. At low tide a single pump was sufficient. Two non-return valves were installed in the sheet pile wall to allow drainage at low tide. Initial problems with sand and silt quickly diminished as the pumps settled down.

Setting-out and monitoring was carried out relative to a site-specific co-ordinated grid using a combination of level, theodolite and electronic distance measurement. Cofferdam movement and island fill settlement were continuously monitored and recorded throughout the contract.

The bearing capacity of the island surface fill was then determined using plate bearing tests, the intention being to assess settlement that could occur under the caisson legs before sinking. The tests indicated a maximum settlement of 15mm at a pressure of 300kN/m². This provided confidence that premature differential settlement would not occur. The cofferdam was completed on February 9th 1998.

Caisson construction was then clear to proceed and the first concrete was poured one week later.

4.4 Construction of Caisson

The caisson is essentially a rectangular concrete hollow box with plan dimensions 27.9m by 13m and height 14.5m. It has 10 discrete cells each nominally 4.5m by 4.5m to provide adequate area for grabbing operations. The perimeter and central walls are of reinforced concrete construction as are the cross walls for a height of 4.6m above toe level only. Above this the temporary cross walls comprise 60 No. 10 tonne precast concrete beams 900mm by 900mm which provide both lateral stability to the NS walls and additional ballast to assist in sinking operations.

With the island fill in place, a concrete blinding layer was placed and the steel cutting shoes fixed in place before the first concrete pour. Concrete was placed in 3 lifts with a total of 42 pours. Initially the caisson was cast to a height of 8.6m in lifts of 2.6m and 6m respectively. After the first sinking of 6.5m, the third lift, 5.9m high was poured. The pouring sequence was planned in a symmetrical fashion in order to keep the structure balanced during all stages of construction. The caisson displacements were continuously measured and recorded during construction and sinking.

Kwikastrip starter bars were used at locations of future concrete-to-concrete intersection i.e. internal slabs, walls etc. The Kwikastrip was fixed flush with the concrete wall and was therefore protected from damage during excavation.

4.5 Sinking of Caisson

Sinking

It was planned to sink the caisson by systematically grabbing from within the hollow cellular structure, thereby undermining the supports and allowing it to drop under its own weight. Calculations

indicated that this would work well for the first 4m but thereafter, as skin friction on the external walls increased, additional means were likely to be required if the sinking was to continue.

Additional features were therefore incorporated in the caisson:

- 3 No.150mm diameter sleeves were cast in vertically at each corner, which if required would allow rock anchors to be inserted and jacked off plates positioned on top of the walls. These could, in theory provide an additional 300 tonne downward force at each corner if required.
- A manifold was installed for the injection of compressed air through the walls of the caisson. This comprised a 100mm dia. pipe network feeding 35mm dia. outlets located at 1500mm centres, 1m above the wall toe level. This would allow compressed air to be forced out and along the outside face of the walls thereby reducing skin friction.

As noted previously, the caisson was initially cast to a height of 8.6m above the sand island in 2 lifts. Sinking by grab excavation then commenced. Two 50 tonne cranes were located within the cofferdam and occasionally on the Bull Wall. The grabbing was carried out in a symmetrical fashion around the centroid of the caisson to ensure uniform vertical displacement. Spoil was discharged within the cofferdam and removed by excavator and dump truck. Sinking commenced on April 29th and by May 20th, the caisson had dropped 6.5m to -4.0 m.O.D (i.e. 6.5m below island level) without major difficulty.

The third lift, 5.9m high, was poured to complete the caisson structure. The second sinking then commenced with the caisson sinking a further 3.2m to -7.2m.O.D without problems.

CAISSON UNDER CONSTRUCTION

FIG 8.

As it approached the lower gravel layer however, the rate of sinking slowed dramatically. It became immediately obvious that undermining the caisson alone was not going to achieve the final drop. A combination of grabbing, air lifting, chiselling and compressed air were used to achieve the last 2m drop:

- A crane suspended air-line allowed the suction of material from close to the cutting shoe i.e. in areas that were not accessible by grab.
- A chisel fabricated on site using an arrangement of sheet piles welded together and attached to the crane line permitted excavation and removal of stiff material adjacent to the cutting edges.
- Compressed air was pumped through the above-mentioned manifold which reduced skin friction on the outer walls.
- A 2.0m deep perimeter trench was excavated around the caisson.

On July 8th, 71 days after sinking had begun, the caisson had dropped 11.7m to its final toe level of -9.2m.O.D. The average rate of sinking had been approximately 250mm/day, with a maximum drop in one day of almost 1m. Fig.9 charts the daily progress of the caisson. A check on the caisson indicated that it had not moved more than 100mm from the initial setting-out

FIG 9.

location and that it had sunk almost completely in plumb, the maximum differential height between any two corners being 16mm.

Control of Sinking

From the outset, both ESBI and Jons considered that control of caisson sinking was critically important. If the caisson went out of plumb the situation could be extremely difficult to remedy.

To achieve uniform sinking, the basic rules in the construction/sinking methodology were:

- The caisson should be cast symmetrically about its centre of gravity.
- Excavation should proceed symmetrically about the centre of gravity until significant differential movement had taken place whereupon excavation should then be concentrated in the area 'hanging-up' until the caisson has levelled out again.

- The profile of soil below the caisson toe should be checked continuously throughout sinking operations by dipping, to determine the extent of overbreak. The soil profile would then be analysed to determine where excavation should be concentrated and which method or combination of methods should be used.

This basic approach was used successfully for the first 9.7m of sinking without the need for additional assistance. During construction of the first 2 lifts some settlement did occur in the NW corner before excavation commenced. To counteract this, excavation was concentrated on the southern bays and the caisson was re-levelled successfully. As the stiff gravel layer was approached however, sinking became more problematic and in addition to the normal grabbing, a combination of the supplementary methods noted above were needed i.e. air lifting, chiselling and compressed air. The same systematic approach to excavation which had been applied to the soft strata was also used for the final 2m sinking.

The only incident during the sinking process that gave cause for concern was the sudden drop of the caisson of almost 1 metre over the space of a few seconds. Fortunately, due to symmetry of excavation, it had sunk almost in plumb and did not require remedial levelling works. It did result however, in a more cautious approach being adopted to the follow-on excavation work.

A significant parameter which had to be addressed in advance of sinking was the effect of seepage due to differential water levels inside and outside the caisson. Excavation within the caisson tended to create an overbreak trough which was, at deepest, approximately 1.0m below the cutting shoes which were then effectively supported on a grillage of raised

TOP VIEW OF CAISSON

embankments. Sudden undermining of the caisson because of seepage of water from outside to inside through these embankments could dramatically increase the rate of sinking and throw the caisson out of plumb. Balanced control of water level within the cofferdam and caisson was regarded as a key factor in dealing with this effect. The water level inside the cofferdam was therefore controlled and held at a value of +1.0m.O.D.

4.6 General Construction of Pumphouse

Concrete Plug

With the caisson in its final position, the next task was to seal it by means of a concrete plug poured below water which would wedge between the sloped cutting edges. Before this could be done, however, it was necessary to prepare the inside faces of the cutting edges in order to provide a proper bond between the caisson and the plug concrete. A team of divers (Irish Diving Consultants Ltd.) descended over 10m through the water-filled caisson and checked for and removed any material adhered to the inside walls. They also carried out a survey of the soil profile by measuring the distance between the cutting shoe and the soil. On completion of the inspection and preparation works, the concrete plug was poured and the caisson sealed. The plug comprising 1080cu.m of Grade C50 concrete was placed under water using two pumps over a seven hour period starting at 4:30 a.m. on July 13th. The higher strength concrete was used in order to achieve a faster set. The use of an underwater concrete admixture was considered unnecessary.

Superstructure

When the plug concrete had achieved the requisite strength, the caisson was pumped dry. Concrete laitance was removed and the top surface of the plug prepared before placing the permanent floor slab concrete 'in the-dry'. The internal walls, platforms and finally the roof slab were then constructed within the dry pumphouse to complete the structure.

The next task was to remove the concrete bulkheads in the north wall and install the dambeams. This required the provision of a dry working area outside the pumphouse wall. Sheet piles were driven to form a small 'blister' cofferdam 13m by 3m against the north face. The area within this cofferdam is currently being excavated and a 3m deep concrete plug will be placed with surface 500mm below the intake invert level. The area within the cofferdam will then be pumped dry to provide the required working area. The bulkheads will be then removed using a combination of jack hammers and concrete saws. The Meehanite guides will

INTERNAL PIER

then be fixed in place using chemical anchors. The dambeams will be installed to seal the Pumphouse. Finally, the 'blister' cofferdam will be removed.

4.7 Construction Problems

Access to the Pumphouse for mechanical and electrical contractors to commence drumscreen erection was required on the 1st October 1998 thereby dictating a substantial completion period of 12 months. From the beginning of the contract it was obvious to all parties that the programme left little room for error. Both ESBI and Jons adopted a proactive approach to the project management of all construction activities. On-site weekly meetings, monthly progress meetings and regular workshops were held to allow interaction between client, consultant, resident engineer and contractor in order to pre-empt problems and develop solutions in advance.

One problem, in this case one which was foreseen, was the likelihood of difficulty in sinking the caisson as the stiff gravels were approached. As can be seen from the sinking graph, Fig.9, the rate did slow considerably. However, the aforementioned contingency measures which had been put in place worked quite effectively.

A particular problem was the unforeseen depth of concrete laitance which formed on the surface of the underwater concrete plug. This laitance varied in depth from 0.5m to 1.5m and because of its location, at the bottom of the chamber, removal was extremely difficult. The material resembled stiff clay and could only be excavated by hydraulic mini-excavator which deposited it in skips for removal by crane.

Another problem, common to most sites in Ireland, is the poor weather conditions. Fortunately, less than one week was lost on the site due to bad weather.

In conclusion, the job, with a very tight construction period coupled with high liquidated damages if work was not

completed on time, meant that all involved in the project were under continuous pressure. The key date for handover was successfully achieved which was a credit to all involved.

4.8 Pumphouse Ancillary Works

In addition to the Pumphouse itself, the civil contract included within its scope a number of ancillary activities as follows:

- To provide access to the Pumphouse and to permit construction of the culvert thrust block, a number of service pipe bridge supports had to be removed. A new bridge section was constructed comprising twin steel trusses spanning 24m over the immediate Pumphouse access area. This allowed removal of the existing steel portal frames and provided clear access to the Pumphouse.
- A reinforced concrete thrust block was constructed to resist the horizontal forces in the rising main as it changed from an above ground pipe to a buried culvert. The bend within the thrust block was formed using Glass Reinforced Plastic as the internal permanent shutter.
- An access bridge spanning approximately 16.0m over the Bull Wall was constructed to provide a support platform for the busmain and access for pump maintenance.
- The thrust block, pipe bridge structure and pre-cast concrete access bridge were all supported by CFA piles.
- Sheet piling was driven parallel to the Bull Wall between the Pumphouse and the jetty to protect the Bull Wall against possible damage from dredging works. Rock armour was also placed adjacent to the wall to protect the dredged bed profile.
- Removal of temporary works, main sheetpile cofferdam, 'blister' cofferdam and sand island.

- This final activity will be the dredging and disposal at sea of 40,000cu.m of riverbed material.

5. DAMBEAMS, SCREENS, GUIDES and GANTRY CRANE

5.1 Dambeams

The 2 No. 6.5 tonne maintenance & inspection dambeams are an essential feature of the C.W. pumphouse, their purpose being to isolate the chambers from the intakes through to the pumps. On such occasions, the screens associated with the chamber in question are removed and replaced with a dambeam to seal the chamber. Each dambeam is designed to withstand a maximum head of 11 metres over a span of 5 metres and height of 4 metres approximately. The dambeam structure consists of skin plate welded to UC beams 267mm deep at 500mm centres and vertical RSC stiffeners 254mm deep at 600mm centres approximately. The beams are tapered down to meet vertical RSC's 152mm deep. The dambeams have an epoxy paint finish with time to first maintenance of 10 to 20 years. Sealing is achieved by 'J'-seals bearing on the lintel plates & downstream flanges of the guides, and an 'L'-seal seating on the cill. Each dambeam is divided in two for ease of transportation.

5.2 Screens

Coarse Screens

The 3.8 tonne coarse screens, in galvanised-plus-paint finish and with 51mm clearance between bars, protect the drum screens from large debris. Under normal operating conditions, the coarse screens are located at the front of both intakes within the downstream slot of the 'E'-shaped guides.

The screen structure, designed to withstand a head loss of 2 metres over the same span and height as the dambeams, consists of central vertical plates and horizontal plates at approximately 900mm centres shaped down to meet vertical RSC's 203mm deep. The panels outlined by the main structure consist of vertical flats at 61mm centres. With a solidity ratio of 0.2, the coarse screen has a negligible effect on the flow. Each screen is fitted with 10 No. replaceable sacrificial anodes of alloyed aluminium, 8 No. to protect the screens and 2 No. to protect the guides. These anodes have an estimated service life of 6 to 10 years, but routine monitoring of their condition is recommended given the possible variation in the electrolyte.

Smolt Screens

In response to Fisheries Legislation, smolt screens in galvanised-plus-paint finish are

DRUMSCREEN AT ROOF DECK LEVEL

placed within the upstream slots of the 'E'-shaped guides to prevent young salmon being drawn into the C.W. system during the smolt season between mid-March and mid-May.

The 2 No. 3.8 tonne smolt screens, with the same overall dimensions and split construction as the coarse screens, were also designed to withstand 2 metres head loss. The screen structure consists of central vertical plates and horizontal members at approximately 900mm centres shaped down to meet vertical side plates. The panels thus

delineated are spanned by 25mm x 12mm weldmesh backed by vertical stiffening bars downstream. The solidity ratio of 0.35 will have a smoothing effect on the flow without significantly affecting the pump efficiency.

Each screen is fitted with 2 No. sacrificial anodes of alloyed aluminium which have an estimated service life of 6 to 10 years as they will be submerged for less than 20% of their lifetime.

5.3 Guides

The guides are fabricated in a double-slotted 'E'-shape, the downstream slots

Gantry Crane

FIG 10

accommodating the coarse screens / dambeams and the upstream slots accommodating the smolt screens in springtime.

Meehanite SG cast iron, of which the guides, and cill & lintel plates are fabricated, is a material with good corrosion resistance in its as-cast state. Additional protection is provided in the form of epoxy paint. Each guide is broken into three segments, the two lowest being approximately 4.3 metres in length and the top segment half this length, the maximum length being limited by the casting process.

5.4 Gantry Crane

The 8-tonne capacity gantry crane with a coverage area of 15m x 6.5m comprises a bi-directional overhead travelling hoist with IP66 protection mounted on a steelwork frame. The hoist consists of a motor-driven double wire rope drum connected to a lifting beam with a pair of automatic counterweight-operated grab/release hooks engaging through identical lifting lugs on all screens and dambeams.

The galvanised-plus-painted crane frame consists of four rigidly connected portal frames with gantry rails. It is an all-bolted construction to minimise distortion during galvanising. Universal Column sections were used throughout based on a minimum lifetime-loss-of-metal allowance of 5mm.

6. DESIGN and SUPERVISION

The Works were designed and the construction supervised by the staff of ESB International. The EIS and plume modelling of the estuary was also carried out by ESBI. The Contractor for the Works described in the paper was Jons Civil Engineering Co. Ltd., Duleek, Co. Louth. Dr. Eric Farrell of Trinity College Dublin was retained by Jons as Geotechnical Consultant for the temporary works.

7. REFERENCES

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A. Civil Engineering Structures

	Length m	Width m	Formation Level m.O.D.	Concrete Quantity m ³	Shuttering m ²	Reinforcement Quantity Tonnes
1. C.W. Pumphouse	27.9	13.0	-9.2	2450	5400	500
2. Thrust Block	10.0	6.2	-1.25	250	330	37.5
3. Access Platform	18.0	21.0	+6.5	542	50	10.5

B. Mechanical Plant

	Number	Supplier
1. Drumscreens	2	E. Beaudrey & Cie, Paris, France
2. C.W. pumps	2	KSB, Frankenthal, Germany
3. Auxiliary Pumps	2	Flygt/ITT, Hanover, Germany
4. Gantry Crane	2	Ballinphellic Engineering Ltd. Cork
5. Electro-Chlorination Plant	-	De Nora, Milan, Italy
6. Rotostrainer	1	Noggerath GMBH, Ahnsen, Germany.

C. Screen Mesh Sizes

Smolt Screens	25mm x 12mm
Drumscreens	5mm x 5mm
Rotostrainer	12mm x 2.5mm

D. 160 MW Steam Turbine CW Pumping Requirement

Maximum Capacity of Pump m ³ /sec	5.5
No. of Pumps	2
Normal Flow/Pump m ³ /sec	4.7

E. Contractors

1. Main Civil Contractor	Jons Civil Engineering Co. Ltd.,
2. Site Investigation	Site Investigations Ltd.
3. Piling	Kvaerner/Cementation Ltd.
4. Diving Services	Irish Diving Consultants Ltd.
5. Precast concrete	Banagher Concrete Ltd.,
6. Pipe Bridge Steelwork	Joseph Murphy Structural Engineers Ltd.
7. Coarse screens, Smolt screens and Dambeams	Steele & Co. Ltd.
8. Meehanite Guides	Brian Donkin Foundry Ltd.
9. Dredging	Irish Dredging Co. Ltd

APPENDIX 1 - TECHNICAL DATA